

The Use of Technology in the Post-method Pedagogy at the Secondary Level in Bangladesh

Mohammad Ehsanul Islam Khan*

Abstract

Teaching methodologies and techniques have been rapidly changing for the last few decades. The advanced technologies greatly contribute to the changes. The study aims at investigating the needs of technology supported post-method pedagogy to facilitate teaching and learning English among the secondary level students in Bangladesh. The participants of the study were 50 secondary students and 10 EFL teachers teaching at the secondary level. A questionnaire survey was administered to the 50 participants in two segments: the first part was to depict their current status of technology use in the CLT approach in EFL classes; and the second part focused their current needs of effective pedagogy in the post-method approach. 10 EFL teachers were directly interviewed to depict their viewpoints on using technology from the perspectives of post method pedagogical approach. The study found that both the learners and the teachers are interested in the use of technology in implementing classroom activities. The study revealed that the current use of technology for the purpose of language teaching was unsatisfactory. The study proposes some ways of pedagogic use of technology in teaching and learning English from post-method perspectives and shows the means of working it out effectively in the EFL classroom.

Key words: *Post-method, secondary level, audio-visuals, personalized learning, movie segments*

1. Introduction

Over the last two decades, Bangladesh experienced a critical condition with CLT in the fields of EFL teaching and learning. CLT was first introduced for the betterment of the EFL pedagogy in the mid-nineties of the last century that has been completely proved to be a failure with time in terms of acquiring a second language like English other than

* Mohammad Ehsanul Islam Khan, Lecturer, Department of English, Manarat International University, Dhaka, Bangladesh; email: ehsan.tangail@gmail.com

Bangla. Researchers like Huda (2013) and Shurovi (2014) also believe the same. Other researchers opined that CLT is ‘not working effectively’ (Iqbal-e-Rasul, 2016) or requires a ‘change’ (Rahman, 2015). This is because Bangladeshi EFL students could not utilize the CLT method for language learning. Even, the teachers could not utilize this method appropriately over the last two decades indeed though Podder (2016) opines that the teachers are not the only responsible for this failure. In consequence, our students could not get the positive result in EFL learning.

Now-a-days people do not even think about a single moment without any technological usage. Particularly, the teenagers are now completely captivated by technology. That trend has also touched the Bangladeshi EFL teachers and learners. In a large extent, negative impacts of using technology are gaudily exposed though it can be manipulated in teaching and learning significantly. On the other side, technology in CLT approach remained neglected in the EFL classes. Though in the last two decades, technology has emergently progressive. Now-a-days, a significant panorama of overusing technology in Bangladesh is found. So, we must think something different to utilize it instead of thwarting it. So, we must seek for an incorporation of using pedagogical technology and the post-method for our EFL learners. Post-method is the latest addition to language teaching and learning in the developed world. Such pedagogy allows us to go beyond, and overcome the limitations of method-based pedagogy (Kumaravadivelu, 2003). As this is both teacher centered and learner centered; it can facilitate both teaching and learning procedures simultaneously.

Most of our teachers are still incapable to use technology in the classroom. Saxena (2013) considers that the pedagogical technology gives beginners instant access to a profusion of valued facts that ‘leads to learning at much quicker rates than before. But unfortunately our secondary schools are not providing such technological facilities to the teachers and the students. The current using tactics of technology are not adequately appropriate for the context and according to the students’ needs. Depicting the technological support of the secondary level institutions, Podder (2016) alleged:

The schools did not have technology such as CD players, audio and video CDs, computers or laptops and multi-media projectors those which could enhance English language teaching and learning. One of the four schools had a television but that was not for use in teaching English language. (p.43)

Therefore, technology should be deployed with post-method tactics in our EFL education system. After successful accomplishment of the study, the EFL teachers will be able to realize the students’

dissatisfaction with the existing technological privileges of CLT approach they are getting in the EFL classrooms. They will also understand the simultaneous needs of innovative EFL pedagogy and supportive technology for the better understanding of the EFL learners in the post-method condition. The study also aims at stimulating the interaction between the EFL teachers and learners in the language classroom in a more credible way.

2. Review of Literature

Post-method is the latest trend in language pedagogy that put emphasis on the immediate needs of both teachers and learners to facilitate teaching and learning English. Therefore, the teachers must not think even a single class without technological support. Adeyanju (1988) opines that language classes with visual subsidy are more interactive and interesting to the learner than those without visual aids.

Considering ICT application in Bangladeshi ELT context, Ali (2016) ponders that a teacher needs to select the materials, tools and equipment based on the appropriateness and interest to age group of the students, point of the lesson, usable language style, locally available and culturally suitable materials like picture, audio and quality video clips. Rahman (2009) considers that pictures can help individual learners predict, infer, deduce information, and analyze today's world so that it can be brought into today's classroom and expose the learner to new ideas. The effective use of online materials may provide positive spin-offs such as 'authenticity' and 'motivation' for learners much the same as if they were engrossed in the language and culture while studying abroad (Paulsen, 2001). Several studies have observed the needs and ways of utilizing interesting technology like audiovisuals, educative games or other video materials in the EFL classroom. Herron, Hanley & Cole (1995) specify that the visual support in the form of descriptive pictures significantly improve comprehension in language. So, visual materials can improve the pedagogic quality in the EFL classrooms. Bajrami and Ismailia (2016) think that while viewing the video materials, students can put themselves in the vivid atmosphere created by the video materials and understand the pragmatics of the language used by the characters.

3. Research Methodology

The study applied a questionnaire survey and teacher interview to collect data. The participants were 50 secondary students and 10 EFL teachers teaching at the secondary level in Bangladesh. The first segment of the questionnaire was set for bringing out the perception of the students to measure their satisfaction level with the existing language pedagogy and technological support. The second segment was about the students' current

needs of EFL pedagogy with supportive technology. The researcher selected different secondary schools to collect data for the study. They aged between 14 and 16 years old and were selected from ten different institutions. Ten EFL teachers were also interviewed on different areas of teaching to elucidate their relevant viewpoints in a qualitative approach.

4. Findings and Discussion

4.1. Result of Students' Questionnaire

A questionnaire having two segments of 10 relevant questions was distributed to the 50 students of class nine and ten who are considered to be the secondary level students in Bangladesh. First segment of the questionnaire having four questions was set to get the closed end information about their satisfaction level with the current support of technology and pedagogy in their EFL classes.

Table1: Students' satisfaction with the existing support of technology

SL	Questions	Yes	No	Sometimes
1	Do your teachers frequently use audiovisual aids in the English class?	0%	32 (64%)	18 (36%)
2	Does the existing CLT approach in the classroom help you learn basic English language skills?	9 (18%)	35 (70%)	6 (12%)
3	Do you find the study materials more authentic when your teachers use technological aids?	27 (54%)	23 (46%)	0
4	Do you communicate in English in the EFL classroom?	4 (8%)	36 (72%)	10 (20%)

Table-1 shows the students' satisfaction with the technological facilities in the current pedagogy. It is found that 64% participants opined that their teachers do not generally use audio-visual aids in the English classes in Dhaka city though 36% participants admitted that their teachers sometimes use audio-visual aids in the class. In general, 70% of the students are not satisfied with the current communicative language teaching approach in terms of learning the basic skills. Particularly, 54% of the participants find the study materials more interesting when their teachers use technological aids. Only 18% students communicate in English in the EFL classroom whereas 72% students do not use English to communicate in the EFL classes. However, 20% students sometimes use English to communicate. The second segment of the questionnaire having six relevant questions was distributed to the same participants to bring out

the information about their current needs of technological facilities in the language classrooms.

Table-2: Students' needs of technological facilities in the EFL classroom

SL	Questions	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
1	I think using technological games in the class can enhance my English language skills.	40 (80%)	5 (10%)	3 (6%)	2 (4%)	0
2	I feel interested in learning English if the teacher uses audio-visual teaching materials.	45 (90%)	3 (6%)	2 (4%)	0	0
3	I consider watching movie to improve my English language skills with new vocabularies.	30 (60%)	10 (20%)	5 (10%)	5 (10%)	0
4	Video materials in the classroom decrease my anxiety and tightness in English language learning.	30 (60%)	10 (20%)	10 (20%)	0	0
5	I feel comfortable to get involved in internet based personalized learning.	25 (50%)	5 (10%)	15 (30%)	5 (10%)	0
6	I think English teachers should use more audio-visual materials in the classroom.	35 (70%)	10 (20%)	5 (10%)	0	0

Table-2 depicts a statistical inquiry of the answers given by the students revealed that on a general level, students considered the use of technological games as effective to develop English language skills. 90% of the students strongly agreed that using games in English classes could facilitate the learning of the English language. Almost all of the participants (96%) found audio-visual aids to be useful in developing their language skills as well as keep them interested in partaking classroom activities during the audiovisual teaching materials. More than half of the participants strongly agreed that watching movie segments in the class can improve their English language skills with new vocabularies. Approximately 80% of the students agreed to the affirmation that the use of video materials in their lessons reduced their anxiety and tightness in learning English language. It is mentionable that assimilation of internet based personalized learning has not been yet completely popular though a large number of teenagers use Facebook and internet in Bangladesh. Still, 60% of the participants are involved in internet based learning. In general, ninety percent of the participants opined that their EFL teachers should use

more audio-visual materials in the classroom to support them improve their English language skills.

4.2. Findings from Teacher Interviews

Ten EFL teachers of different schools were directly interviewed to get related information about using technology and post-method pedagogy in the EFL classrooms with six relevant questions. They were also independent to give their valuable opinions for the development of EFL education in Bangladesh.

Table-3: Teachers' opinions on EFL pedagogy and use of innovative technology

SL	Questions	Always	Sometimes	Never
1	Do you use audiovisual teaching materials in the classroom?	2 (20%)	4 (40%)	4 (40%)
2	Do you implement self-made activity in the language classroom?	1 (10%)	2 (20%)	7 (70%)
3	Do you think that using games or viewing movies can facilitate learning of English language skills?	8 (80%)	2 (20%)	0
4	Have you ever received any formal training on using technology in the class?	4 (40%)	–	6 (60%)
5	Do you think the sociable usage of technology can support you to master the class?	7 (70%)	1 (10%)	2 (20%)
6	Do your institutions have adequate technological support to use in the English language classrooms?	1 (10%)	–	9 (90%)

It is found that only 60% teachers use audio-visual teaching materials in the class, though not frequently. Notably, 70% of the teachers are still trying to implement CLT for teaching English in the EFL classroom. Only 30% teachers like post-method in the EFL class whereas 20% of them do not frequently use it. Eighty percent of the teachers feel that using games or viewing movie segments can facilitate learners' learning of English language skills. But inconsiderately 60% of the teachers have not received any training on using technology in the class. Most of the teachers (70%) assert that the effective use of technology can support them to master the class, though 20% of them disagree with that opinion. Just the opposite panorama, 90% teachers admit that their institutes have not the adequate technological support to use in the EFL classrooms. During the interviews, all the teacher participants were asked to give their opinions about using technology in the class. 30% teacher-participants stated that they prioritized students' needs in the English language classes.

Teacher (T1) remarked:

Most of the time, science teachers usually use projector in the classes. English teachers in that case do not get the priority always... I follow CLT approach though sometimes I need to fulfill the immediate needs to assist the students.

During the interview another teacher (T2) informed:

My institution has adequate technological supports; but we, the English teachers do not use frequently though most of us believe the pedagogic use of technology can hasten the learning of the students and lessen our labor in the class.... I follow post-method pedagogy to some extent, but not completely.

One of the interviewee (T3) confirmed the present researcher:

I use technology in the classroom at least twice a week. Even sometimes, I use Facebook to upload the study materials for the students. They also enjoy it... I always prioritize the students' needs. I never fix on a single pedagogy for EFL teaching.

Some of the participants have not received any training on pedagogic use of technology in the classroom though they admitted that the use of effective technology can help them master the class. In this connection, a teacher (T4) disclosed that:

I do not use technology because I am not able to use such technological equipment. Moreover, if any problems occur in the middle of the class, I won't be able to solve it. I am using CLT in the EFL classrooms.

One of the teachers (T5) commented:

I do not think technology always support me to master the class. Very often, whiteboard and marker helps me to make my students understand the lesson in a better way. Regarding pedagogy, I prefer to combine GTM and Direct Method to CLT.

During the interview, a teacher (T6) concluded:

I have never received any training of using technology effectively in the classroom. So, I do not use technology. I use CLT to teach English at school.

It is worth mentioning that several teachers used post-method pedagogy in the classes though they were not clearly aware of the concept of this pedagogy. Some teachers opined that if the technology-based games and movies were used in the class for language practice, the learners would be tremendously benefitted. Therefore, it can be said that

students are interested to learn through innovative and attention-grabbing technological support which is also the key tactic of post method pedagogy in learning a second/foreign language other than the native tongue. Still, in Bangladesh the students are not getting technological support adequately to learn English language skills properly.

5. Recommendations

The study recommends some major needs and modifications of current EFL pedagogy after getting the related information. A new approach combining CLT, Grammar Translation Method and Direct Method can be adopted as a way in the current post-method condition. YouTube channels, Facebook groups and different educative websites should be properly utilized by the teachers for teaching with more credibility. In this regard, Ayman Sadiq's '10 Minute School' can be an effective approach to facilitate learning by providing solutions and elucidations of different topics enriched by a variety of creative teaching and learning devices. Such virtual schooling serves pedagogical purposes in the post-method. Mobile phones are now quite popular among the teenagers.

The teachers can utilize the mobile phones for teaching pronunciation or vocabularies through different language learning applications. Teachers should adopt the current technological facilities according to the interest of the teenage learners. In that case, some pedagogic websites can be supportive for the EFL teachers to utilize during teaching in the EFL classrooms. These are also supportive for the personalized learning of the learners through internet. The teacher may also show movies in the class for the enrichment of students' vocabulary in English language. The students can watch the movie segments in their classroom on the projector screen. After that the teacher may get them involved in different classroom activities. Animated cartoon movies with subtitles can be supportive in this regard. Writing movie summaries, taking notes on important vocabularies, group work or role play can be the different form of classroom activities that a teacher can adopt. To make our classes more effective, the teachers may arrange different types of educative games with authentic visual texts related to his lesson. Indeed, the practice of games in EFL classrooms is an approach to render more "interesting, enjoyable, and effective" teaching (Uberman, 1998).

6. Conclusion

The Post-method pedagogy requires new and flexible tactics for both EFL and ESL teaching and learning. In the EFL context of Bangladesh, it is high time we started using post-method pedagogy for the betterment of our students. In that case, use of technology in more

effective ways is significant that the current paper actually affirms. There were enormous integers of constructive and destructive notions to education technology. Nevertheless, step by step as technology was encompassed by the educational institutions, they appreciated the technological significance in education. So, using technology is an eye-catching teaching tactic for the EFL teachers in Bangladesh. Though, it may not be applicable to all types of institutions for the socio-economic condition of the country. Still, we can long for such an environment in the educational institutes if government of Bangladesh supports in this regard by setting up a language lab in every schools and colleges. Even in universities, language lab is considered as a fascinating place to pass the leisure during daytime of classes.

References

- Adeyanju, J. L. (1988). The application of educational technology in pre-primary education. *Journal of Educational Media and Technology*, 2(1), 73-79.
- Allan, M. (1985). *Teaching English with Video*; Longman: Avon.
- Ali, M. (2016). Application of ICT in English Language Teaching in Bangladesh: Prospect, Problems and Solution; *ASA University Review*, 10(1), 139-152.
- Bajrami, L and Ismailia, M. (2016). The Role of Video Materials in EFL Classrooms; *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 232, 502-506.
- Canning-Wilson, C. (2000). Role of Video in the F/SL Classroom; 69-76. In S. Riley, S. Troudi and C. Coombe. (ed.) *Teaching, Learning and Technology, TESOL Arabia, 1999 Conference Proceedings*, March, 8-10.
- Education Week. (2016). *Technology in Education: An Overview*; Published on 5th February 2016, Retrieved from: www.edweek.org
- English in Action. (2009). An Audit of a Range of English Language Teacher Training and Adult Provision, *English in Action Baseline Study 5*.
- Herron, C, Hanley, J. and S. Cole. (1995). A comparison study of two advance organizers for introducing beginning foreign language students to video, *Modern Language Journal*, 79 (3), 387-394.
- Huda, M. E. (2013). Post Method Pedagogy and ELT in Bangladesh, *Global Journal of Human Social Science*, 13(07), 2013.
- Iqbal-e-Rasul (2016). The Situation of Communicative Language Teaching Approach in Bangladesh—An Assessment, *UITS Journal*, 5(1).
- Kumaravadivelu, B. (2003). *Beyond methods: Macro-strategies for language teaching*. New Haven, CT: Yale University Press.

- Paulsen, P. (2001). New era trends and technologies in foreign language learning: An annotated bibliography. *Interactive Multimedia Electronic Journal of Computer-Enhanced Learning*, 4(6), 36-48.
- Podder, P. (2016). Challenges of Implementing CLT at Secondary Level of Education in Bangladesh, *The EDRC Journal of Learning and Teaching*, 01(01), 34-45.
- Rahman, M. M. (2009). The Use of Visuals in Teaching EFL Classes in Bangladesh, *DIU Journal of Business and Economics*, 4(1&2).
- Rahman, M. S. (2015). Implementing CLT at Higher Secondary Level in Bangladesh: A Review of Change Management, *Journal of Education and Practice*, 6(2).
- Saxena, S. (2013). How important is use of technology in education. *EdTech Review*, Retrieved from: <http://edtechreview.in/news/681-technology-in-education>.
- Shurovi, M. (2014). CLT and ELT in Bangladesh: Practice and Prospect of Speaking and Listening, *Journal of Language Teaching and Research*, Academy Publishers: Finland, 5(6), 1263-1268, doi:10.4304/jltr.5.6.1263-1268.
- Uberman, A. (1998). The use of games for vocabulary presentation and revision, *Forum*. Accessed on 10th February, 2018, Retrieved from: <http://exchanges.state.gov/forum/vols/vol36/no1/p20.htm>
- Valarmathi, K. E. (2011). Mobile assisted language learning. *Journal of Technology for ELT*, Volume-II, No-2; 1-8.
- Zahin, A. (2015). *Teacher Talk Time (TTT) in EFL classrooms in Bangla and English Medium Schools*. BA Thesis, Department of English & Humanities, BRACU.